

ANALYSIS OF KINARAGAN AETA ENGLISH ORAL ACCURACY

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational study is aimed at understanding the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken students in Limay National High School. The locale of the study was the Limay National High School where most of the Aeta Magbuken students are studying. The respondents of the study were the fifteen (15) Aeta Magbuken high school students. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the respondents.

The data gathered was encoded and statistically processed using statistical software called PASW Statistics version 18. Statistical tools such as mean, pearson product moment correlation (r) and coefficient of determination (t -test) were utilized to analyze data and address the specific questions enumerated in the Statement of the Problems in Chapter I of this study. Weighted mean was used to present result of survey-questionnaires of the factors affecting the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken students in terms of community-related factors (learning resources, lifestyle and exposure to media, teacher-related factors (teaching strategies and attitudes toward Aeta Magbuken students), and student-related factors (initiative, self-esteem and exposure to literature). Coefficient of determination (t -test) and Pearson product correlation (r) were used to determine the significant relationship of the factors affecting the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students. From the data gathered in the study, the following were the findings:

First, the community related factors in terms of learning resources present in the community sometimes affect the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students. Also, the lifestyle of the Aeta Magbuken students sometimes affects their oral English accuracy. Furthermore, the Aeta Magbuken students disagree that they are exposed to media which affects their oral English accuracy.

The initiative of the Aeta Magbuken students sometimes affect their oral English accuracy. In addition, their self-esteem also sometimes affect their oral English accuracy. Moreover, the Aeta Magbuken students agree that they are exposed to literature which does not affect their oral English accuracy.

Based on the findings of the study, the Aeta Magbuken students agree that the teachers' teaching strategies affect their oral English accuracy. On the other hand, the attitudes of the teachers towards Aeta Magbuken students sometimes affect their oral English accuracy.

It was concluded that the Aeta Magbuken students meet the expectations in the use of prepositions, while needs improvement in the use of verb tenses, in the use of simple sentence structure, and in the use of subject-verb agreement which affects their oral English accuracy.

Likewise, there is significant relationship between the community- related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students. The teacher- related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students also has significant-relationship. Finally, it was found out that there is a significant relationship between the student- related factors and oral English Accuracy of the students. A conceptual framework was developed to provide a better understanding of the significant relationships between the given factors.

Hence, it was recommended that the teachers are recommended to expose the students with community learning resources through having field trips in other community nearby that has learning resources present like museums, public mini library and nature parks. Through this, the teacher can help to reach out the students' need even those are not present in their community. To teachers, since the community of Aeta Magbuken students are lacking when it comes to media, they must expose the students to use different technologies like computer, laptop, LCD, DVD, etc.

The teachers must also let the students, especially the students to manipulate and use those media in class activities.

The teachers should create an English speaking environment by encouraging the students to use English in the classroom to make it a habit, letting them watch films or videos in English and the teachers should also use English in the classroom frequently so that the students have more exposure to the language.

The teachers should also identify the strategies that best meet their language learners' immediate needs, and they can explore students' reaction to their learning approaches for the second language. Moreover, they can use classroom research as a tool for showing the language learners that the teaching strategies in second language acquisition really work. Teachers should provide opportunities to increase verbal interaction in classroom activities to help ensure that students are exposed to as many different types of authentic language as possible and allow students opportunities to practice using the target language. Planning for more group and pair work during lessons would help to do this. The following strategies and techniques could be incorporated more into practice by teachers to further improve the language support given to learners. Furthermore, they should integrate up-to-date materials and supplementary resources in addition to the English text books. This can help them capture students' attention to learn English successfully.

The teacher should give the students more opportunity of collaborative learning by means of pair or group discussion to voice out their opinions with increased confidence when speaking L2. Having daily conversation, students experience a greater sense of ability and confidence to speak English. In this case, when students have the confidence to speak the language they can now have the initiative to speak English without hesitation. The teachers should first improve the performance conditions by giving their students time to prepare for a speaking task, teaching the

students how to use mind map to generate ideas and giving students enough time to perform their tasks. Teachers should help their students overcome inhibition and shyness by having friendly, helpful and cooperative behaviors to make students feel comfortable when speaking in the class, reminding students not to worry about making mistakes and giving them clear instructions and sufficient guidance. Teachers should also personalize and simplify the topics in the textbook to make them easier, more interesting and relevant to their lives. They should decide carefully when and how to correct the students' mistakes so that the students are not fearful of making mistakes and the flow of the students' conversation is not destroyed. In addition, they should also encourage students to participate in speaking activities. Finally, the teachers should create an English speaking environment by encouraging the students to use English in the classroom to make it a habit, letting them watch films or videos in English and the teachers should also use English in the classroom frequently so that the students have more exposure to the language. Teachers of English language are recommended to encourage their students to learn literature in order to develop their performance especially in speaking skills.

It is suggested that teachers of English language should consider their students' linguistic abilities and minimize the amount of difficult vocabulary that their students encounter when studying literature. They have to use suitable teaching methods, approaches, strategies and materials that help the students in their acquisition of second language. Teachers are required to modify the difficult literary texts to suit the student's vocabulary without losing the essence of the original text. When studying literature, teachers should maintain a comfortable and friendly atmosphere and design interesting activities that encourage students of literature to read, think and act.

It is recommended that the community must have partnerships with wide range of community organizations like business and government agencies to provide critically needed materials, especially technologies. Also, teachers should establish and foster a community-based early language program through advocacy, Reese (2008). This type of community engagement emphasizes collaboration among school partners and sites, practical training for participants and reciprocal benefits through culturally rich language teaching as students and instructors learn to work with youngsters who are very open to novel ways of expressing ideas in a new language. A model is developed and presented as a concrete example of a successful award-winning program that language teachers might follow.

Teachers are also encouraged to tackle this problem is to find the root of the problem and start from there. If the problem is cultural, that is in your culture it is unusual for students to talk out loud in class, or if students feel really shy about talking in front of other students then one way to go about breaking this barrier is to create and establish your own classroom culture where speaking is the norm. One way to do this is to distinguish your classroom from other classroom desks differently, in groups instead of lines etc.

Finally, language teachers are encouraged to set attainable goals from the start of the year. That is a surefire way for students to see how much they have grown. It is also necessary to give the students opportunity to choose what they learn— this will help them build their self-worth. Try a learning menu or choice board where students get to choose which activities they want to learn.

INTRODUCTION

Language makes communication possible; without it people are unable to convey thoughts and ideas, transmit culture and disseminate information to others. Generally, language is used for meaning-making, either in oral or written forms. According to Gao (2005), “the purpose of acquiring or learning a language is for communication”. Likewise, Canale (2005) stated that “communication is the essential purpose of language”.

In the era of globalization in the twenty-first century, English language is a means of global communication as it is the international language, a major language in the world. English language is used dominantly worldwide for Information Communication Technology (ICT), science, diplomacy, mass media and global business communications (“Language of the Global Economy”) Canale (2006). Its use for occupational purposes is becoming more and more obvious. Furthermore, the British Council stated that “English is the main language of books, newspapers, airports and air-traffic control, international business and academic conferences, science, technology, diplomacy, sport, international competitions, pop music and advertising” (as cited in Dieu & Pauster, 2005). Thus, English is the major window for us to explore and get in touch with the outside world. Clearly, a good command of English is the key to social and economic advancement. Users with a good command of English are presumed to have accurate knowledge of the language and the ability to use the language to achieve their communicative purposes.

Competency in English is important for effective communication as one stands a better chance of being understood when one conveys information accurately and unambiguously. Hence, those who do not know English are at a great disadvantage. However, to achieve the purpose of effective communication, a native or non-native speaker has to possess certain degree of competence (Gao, 2005). Thus, this highlights the notion of communicative competence.

Communicative competence refers to the knowledge about a language and other aspects of communicative language use and the skills in using the knowledge when interacting in actual communication (Canale, 2005; Canale & Swain, 2006). In communicative competence, there is a great deal of emphasis on how to use the language, yet linguistic competence still has its weighty impact in communication. This is because “in order to be able to communicate effectively, learners need an adequate mastery of grammar and vocabulary” (Byrne, 2007 p.11). Thus, this is where the accuracy of spoken English is emphasized.

In this study, accuracy refers to the accuracy in spoken English. According to Baltram and Walton (2010), accuracy in spoken English refers to “utterances as near as to a native speaker’s as possible” in terms of grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation. Moreover, Thornbury (2009) refers to accuracy as the production of grammatical utterances. It means that the attention is on the rules and forms of the language when it is concerned with the accuracy in spoken English. In other words, it is linguistic competence. In terms of accuracy in spoken English, this study focuses on the accuracy of grammar, excluding vocabulary and pronunciation as the learners are the ESL learners where the non-native speakers’ variation in terms of pronunciation is too great and there may be some features of deviation in the vocabulary usage.

Accuracy is the ability to produce error-free speech or the extent to which the language produces in performing a task manifests pausing, hesitation or reformulation Ellis (2006). It is a

student's ability to speak a language in real-life settings, outside of the classroom with the ability to recognize and produce the distinctive grammatical structures of a language and use them effectively in communication. Omaggio (2005), states, oral accuracy includes the ability to communicate verbally in a functional and accurate way in the target language. Speaking without listening produces one sided conversation rather than meaningful dialogue. According to Ur (2007), 'of all the four skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing), speaking seems intuitively the most important. Speaking is the most important skill because it enhances effective communication and increase communicative competence that tends to be the most crucial one. Like in many other countries, the problem in speaking skills is very crucial because researchers investigated this field and came to the conclusion about the students' low level of speaking ability and their inability to speak fluently and accurately. Morozova (2009), teachers must overcome their reluctance in order to change the situation and help students develop their speaking skills with the other skills so that these integrated skills will enhance communication competence.

English as a language has great reach and influence; it is taught all over the world. Snyder (2013), English is the language of power and progress. In the Philippines, it is highly valued not only because it is functional, practical and washes over us constantly, but more importantly, because it is an affordable item, a skill that can be used to increase one's position, respectability and marketability. On the other hand, indigenous people, like all people, need to communicate in their primary language in order to respond to human communications, hence; in order to deal with a world with dynamic language, they should learn to speak English as second language in global communication. Indigenous students, on the whole have a history of achieving below the levels of students whose language background is other than English. This gap of achievement has been reported to be generally greatest in more remote areas and to increase as the grades tested go

higher, Maceey (2008). In the communicative model of second language teaching, instructors help their students develop this body of knowledge by providing authentic practice that prepares students for real-life communication situations.

English ties the gap and joins the people, because it's the only language that greatly connects the whole world together. It can be the bridge to communicate with people who do not speak your native language. Aside from the first language, it is important for Filipinos to learn English as second language because it is the main communication in business. The English language plays a central role in the everyday life of Filipinos as an international center of finance, business, trade and tourism. It is important among Filipinos as a global language. It allows us to communicate with the world using what appears to be the most commonly used language right now. Besides, it is the language of commerce and business and science. It serves as an open door for Filipinos to achieve in the workplace and global competence.

The aim of English language education is to provide learners with the capabilities to understand the language and the ability to both write and speak. If learners are not able to speak English, this aim has not been fully achieved. Thus, it is necessary to study this issue in order to discover if people indeed have problems with speaking, there is good reason to research the matter considering the Aeta Magbuken. Losses of words, frustration, anxiety, grammatical problems etc., are only some of the problems that arise about speaking accuracy. Learning the English as second language makes our future generations better thinkers, boost brain development and bridges cultural system and give economic edge. Those who speak two or more languages can see the world from two or more perspectives. They are more open minded and emphatic; they can constantly try to make a connection. The brain is about connectives. They are always trying to analyze and compose so they can plug in new information.

Learning resources are also one of the contributors for helping a person to acquire easily the second language. Eusebio (2010), having sufficient resources and adequate tools as well as being expose to media will greatly help in the acquisition of the target language. Carino (2012), the government however, is lacking in providing sustainable services and assistance to help the Aetas rebuild their lives. The respondents claimed that aside from hospitalization and scholarship, the government has no current program, services and assistance for the Kinaragan Aetas. Educational assistance was in the form of literacy education specifically the Alternative Learning System (ALS) as well as promotion of children's health and nutrition through feeding programs and medical missions. Evidently, today's economy is increasingly globalized so that many of the Filipinos are interacting across culture in a way they never did before. In such economy, the importance of learning the L2 becomes self-evident.

Aeta students are commonly known for absenteeism and low grades due to inappropriate mindset and lacking of initiative and motivation. Tribal groups specifically Aetas do not have formal schooling because most of them cannot afford to go to exclusive schools and another thing is that the distance is too far from their area. Upon the initial visit of the researchers, they found out that shyness, self-pity and low self-esteem are other factors that also affect their study because mostly, they do not have secondary schools in their area. Therefore, the government implemented the Alternative Learning System (ALS) to the Aetas to educate them. Free educations, full scholarship to college, building schools to the community are only some of the efforts of the government to help them. According to Hon. Jesli Lapus, Former Secretary of Department of Education in 2006, "ALS is expected to provide solutions in areas of conflict, critical thinking, in indigenous people communities and in areas where literacy is needed". Therefore, the research front, it calls for a need to study the oral English accuracy of Kinaragan Aeta high school students.

Hence this leads to the aim of this study which is to examine the related factors affecting the students' oral English accuracy.

Hyde (2011) mentioned that the Ministry of Education is dedicated to ensuring that the cultures and contributions of Aboriginal peoples in British Columbia are reflected in all provincial curricula. To address these topics in the classroom in a way that is accurate and that respectfully reflects Aboriginal concepts of teaching and learning, teachers are strongly encouraged to seek the advice and support of local Aboriginal communities. Aboriginal communities are diverse in terms of language, culture, and available resources; each community will have its own unique protocol to gain support for integration of local knowledge and expertise. To begin discussion of possible instructional and assessment activities, teachers should first contact Aboriginal education coordinators, teachers, support workers, and counsellors in their district who would be able to facilitate the identification of local contacts and resources such as elders, chiefs, tribal or band councils, Aboriginal cultural centers, Aboriginal Friendship Centers, and Métis or Inuit organizations.

For the purposes of provincial or district evaluation, the Ministry of Education defines learning resources as “information represented, accessible or stored in a variety of media and formats, which assists student learning as defined by the learning outcomes of the provincial curriculum.” Learning resources are generally understood to be texts, videos, software, and other materials that assist students to meet the expectations for learning, as defined by provincial or local curricula. Before a learning resource is used in a classroom, it must be evaluated to ensure that criteria such as those for curriculum match, social considerations and age or developmental appropriateness are met.

Learning resources such as newspapers or periodicals that support current events or “the teachable moment” also need to be evaluated for suitability before use in a classroom. Usually, the evaluation of this type of resource relies on the professional expertise and judgment of the classroom teacher. In addition, teachers may wish to consult the various related Ministry of Education publications, including the “Planning Your Program” section of the resource, Shared Learnings. This resource was developed to help all teachers provide students with knowledge of, and opportunities to share experiences with, Aboriginal people in British Columbia.

Whorf (2005) claimed that the language we speak does affect how we think and this shapes how we experience the world. As linguist Guy Deutscher writes, "Since habits of speech are cultivated from the earliest age, it is only natural that they can settle into habits of mind that go beyond language itself, affecting your experiences, perceptions, associations, feelings, memories and orientation in the world." So our language doesn't force us to see only what it gives us words for, but it can affect how we put things into groups. One of the jobs of a child learning language is to figure out which things are called by the same word. In other words, the influence of language isn't so much on what we can think about, or even what we do think about, but rather on how we break up reality into categories and label them. And in this, our language and our thoughts are probably both greatly influenced by our culture. Your culture—the traditions, lifestyle, habits, and so on that you pick up from the people you live and interact with—shapes the way you think, and also shapes the way you talk.

Wilson (2005) mentioned that because of the way their culture shapes their thinking—their ways of knowing—many Aboriginal people say culture is their language. Language patterns are deeply woven into the lives of Aboriginal students, their families and their communities, regardless of their fluency in an Aboriginal language. In fact, language patterns tend to endure for three

generations—a student whose great-grandparents were the most recent Aboriginal language speakers in the family will still be influenced by their language patterns. The first language of some students is an Aboriginal language. As they speak English, these students are constantly translating their thoughts. This process may be difficult as the meaning of the words and the patterns of thinking in their first language may be quite different from English.

For speakers of an Aboriginal language, English can seem very linear and lacking in context. It is important to give students time to articulate their thoughts and to find ways to help them express themselves clearly and comfortably. It is also important to be aware of tone, volume and pitch. Speakers of Aboriginal languages often speak in softer tones. They listen carefully to voice inflection and so may be very sensitive not only to what is being said but how it is being said. Aboriginal people often use humour—there is a lot of laughter in Aboriginal conversations. “The simplicity of our daily life does not indicate that our vocabulary is simple and limited to a few hard-to-gurgle grunts.

Lratim-uba (2010) noted that by the time children arrive kindergarten, they would be able to name more fictional characters from television and radio than people in real life due to the fact that the television and radio than people in real life due to the fact that the television and radio give variety of information well beyond what children might be expected to obtain from primary groups such as the family, the school and the classroom. The broadcast media, including the television and radio are not just mechanical devices for creating worlds of illusions, but are avenues of creating new language with new powers of expressions. These powers of expressions influence English Language usage in the educational sector through the use and misuse of the language. For instance, in an attempt to mobilize the public for action or for a change of attitude; programmes are packaged and presented to reach both rural and urban dwellers without sensitivity to the rules

of the English Language. In addition, commercial and advertisements further mangle the language with incomplete comparisons. These comparisons are heightened by the way sales are implied, suggested and given hint to – almost say things which codes, rules and regulations and good taste forbid. This brings about a generation of children and learners who are unable to express themselves clearly and therefore, unable to write decent language, especially the English Language. This effect is to be expected since programmes of the televisions and radio are largely oral and visual, with little or no opportunity provided for interaction with prints. This deprives children largely oral and visual, with little or no opportunity provided for interaction with prints. This deprives children of the nuances of written expression that involve much review analysis synthesis and evaluation.

Bourke (2006) claimed that various teaching strategies play a more significant role in improving performance for Indigenous students than for other students because the educational disadvantage of Indigenous students is generally higher, which means they might require more significant support from teachers. Research shows that teachers can influence Indigenous students' experiences at school, including enjoyment, engagement, success, attendance and their overall perceptions of school (Craven et al. 2005; Bourke et al. 2006).

There is no evidence that points to a single strategy for the effective teaching of Indigenous students in terms of driving educational achievements. The report *Overcoming Indigenous disadvantage* concluded that research into what makes a quality teacher is varied. Some studies have strongly linked student outcomes with teacher experience and test scores in obtaining qualifications, and other studies have demonstrated that, for secondary students, years of teaching experience and level of teacher qualification are not significant influences. However, the report

noted that there is some research that demonstrates that teachers with a sound knowledge of the subject matter can be a strong predictor of student outcomes (Hill et al. 2005)

The literature points to particular characteristics of teachers and teachers' relationships with their students as affecting educational outcomes for Indigenous students. Many of these characteristics will be underlined by teachers' understanding of Indigenous culture and preferred Indigenous learning styles. The importance of positive teacher–student relationships between Indigenous students and their teachers for the educational achievement of Indigenous students has also been well documented (Maceey 2006). Doyle and Hill (2008) recognized three (3) main characteristics of teachers that can affect Indigenous student attendance and engagement: teachers' interactions and relationships with their students. The skills of the teacher, such as being trained in English as a second language teaching techniques and their experience with teaching in a cross-cultural bilingual situation. The teacher's ability to tailor their teaching approach and structuring of the curriculum to meet the specific needs of Indigenous students.

Ewijk (2007) stated that teachers may either hold low expectations of individual minority students, or unfavorable attitudes toward ethnic minorities groups in general. Both are likely to be noticed by the students at some point, which may then lead them to adjust their efforts and performance downwards.

Teacher ethnicity may positively affect student behavior if a same ethnicity teacher serves as a role model for minority students. Conversely, a different ethnicity teacher may evoke “stereotype threat”. This is the phenomenon that if a stereotype exists that says that people from a certain group perform poorly, a member of this group will indeed start to perform poorly when this negative stereotype about the own group gets activated (Steele & Aronson, 1995). This may happen if ethnic minority students notice the teacher's different ethnicity and expect him/her to share this negative

stereotype. Thinking about the stereotype leads to a fear of being judged or treated according to the stereotype, or simply of confirming the stereotype in their performance, which consequently causes them to perform poorer.

Jones and Allsop (2009) explained that “prepositions are little words but they carry a lot of meaning”. The meaning of prepositions can be literal, metaphorical extension, prototypical, etc. so we must be careful on using it.

Prepositions can consist of one or single word, two or multi words. Prepositions are used all the time in English but is often difficult to know which preposition to use. Even though prepositions may consist of only one or few of words but they play important role in meaning. Each preposition can have different meanings especially on how you will use them in a sentence. That’s why although prepositions are always used in English, it is not easy to choose and decide which appropriate preposition to use.

The researchers found out that ESL learners are having difficulty in which preposition they are going to use in a sentence. The use of prepositions helps people who want to describe or explain specific time, area, position or location. Prepositions must be used properly and precisely, with these in mind, someone who use prepositions will be able to direct the location, position or an area clearly. Each preposition is used differently with different purposes as well. The wrong choice of prepositions can cause misunderstood between people, which is the reason why prepositions are quite significant to be learned in English language.

Chappell and Godfrey (2005) explained some errors on verb tense composition among the students in tertiary level. The subject in the study were asked to explain their errors and their answers were taped for analysis.

Quarters of errors were due to the choice and became the focus of the study's second area of inquiry which is the discourse context of verb errors. The researchers hypothesized that there would be more errors in contexts that required shifts in verb tenses. The results of the study confirmed their hypothesis. Examples of contexts that require shifts in tense are the use of generic present tense in the past tense passages to supply background information and discourse that requires perfects or modals.

The researchers found out that ESL learners' problem is twofold. Firstly, they do not understand how contexts and temporal stands can influence tense use. They do not know the function of tenses in a discourse. As a result, they choose the tenses arbitrarily and often switch tenses at random. It was found in a study of writings by Chapell and Rodby that tense sequence is in the highest rung of difficulty. This is traced to the structural differences between the Tagalog tense system and the English system.

Konig and Gast (2008) stated the main assumption of Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis which describes the similarities and differences between pairs of language and how some factors enable humans to acquire and produce language. It is based on the assumption that foreign language learners resort to habits they acquire in the process of first language acquisition.

First language acquisition and foreign language learning differ fundamentally, especially in those cases where the foreign language is learnt later than a mother tongue and so on the basis of the full mastery of that mother tongue. Every language has its own specific structure. Similarities between the two languages will cause no difficulties, but differences will, due to negative transfer. The student learning task can therefore roughly be defined as the sum of the differences between the two languages. A systematic comparison between mother tongue and the foreign language to be learnt will reveal both similarities and contrasts.

Therefore, in the comparison between native and foreign language lies the key to ease difficulty in foreign language learning. Those elements that are similar to the learners' native language will be simple for him. It is easy for him to construct or produce simple sentences correctly. Those elements that belong to foreign language will be difficult for him because it differs from his L1. The patterns that will cause difficulty in learning, and those that will not difficulty depends on how they will compare systematically the language and the culture to be learned with that native and foreign language.

Murcia and Freeman (2008), stated that in spite of the early introduction and the superficially simple rules of the subject-verb agreement, they still pose problems for the ESL learners at all levels. These students tend to make errors although the subject-verb agreement structure was introduced early to students i.e. when they were in the primary level they still faced problem in acquiring the correct form of it.

The study dealt with the subject-verb agreement in students' written production. The written method is used because of several reasons. The first reason is that written work can test students' comprehension and production of grammatical rules they have already learned in a more appropriate way. Besides, when they are given a chance to use their own topic for their term paper, they can have more freedom to write on the topic that interests them.

There is evidence that students still possess problems in the usage of their subject-verb agreement. Majority of the students have problems in their general rule than sub-rules. Students have problems in subject-verb agreement because they do not have this kind of rule in their L1. Some students did not realize that they made errors since they have problems in this area. Therefore, remedial actions should be taken in order to help them produce a good piece of work.

Relevant Theories

This study was anchored on the theories advocated by Brown (2001) Theory of Motivation (Behaviorist), Lev Vygotsky's (1962) Social Interactionist Theory and Cummins (1994) the Monitor and Affective Filter Theory.

This study is anchored to the Theory of Motivation by Brown (2001) emphasizing the Behaviorist theory. Over the past decades, theorists carried out numerous studies that showed a range of explanations. The definitions suggested may be interpreted in so many ways, "depending on the theory of human behavior you adopt", Brown (2001).

Behaviorists approached motivation in a scientific way in the sense that they carried out some experiments on animals to comprehend how humans are motivated to learn, Slavin (2007). This perspective was influenced by Pavlov (Classical Conditioning), Thorndike (The Law of Effect), and mainly by Skinner (Operant Conditioning). For these scientists, motivation is simply seen as "the anticipation of reward", Brown (2007) they noted that reward acts as a reinforcement as "any consequence that strengthens a behavior". Students for example, when feeling ambitious for a positive reinforcement, push themselves to perform according to prior experience with reward (teacher's praise) when giving a correct answer to win another positive comment (reward). It is noteworthy to point out that behaviorists see that "our actions are at the mercy of external forces such as rewards", Williams & Burden (2007).

The only instance in which the teaching of grammar can result in language acquisition (and accuracy) is when the students are interested in the subject and the target language is used as a medium of instruction. As one of the factors that affects the English speaking accuracy of AetaMagbuken is the teacher related factors wherein teaching strategies, attitudes toward

AetaMagbuken students influence their motivation to learn and to acquire the target language. In other words, the teacher talk meets the requirements for comprehensible input and perhaps with the students' participation, the classroom becomes an environment suitable for acquisition. Consequently, the teacher must provide a non-threatening classroom wherein there is an open and free communication regardless in deviation.

Social interaction theory is an explanation of language development emphasizing the role of social interaction between the developing child and linguistically knowledgeable adults. It is based largely on the socio-cultural theories of Soviet psychologist, Lev Vygotsky (1962). Social interaction plays an important role in the learning process and proposed the zone of proximal development (ZPD) where learners construct the new language through socially mediated interaction. The social interaction approaches rest on the premises of a social-cognitive model, emphasizing the child construction of a social world which then serves as the context of language development. The essentials of this theory which differentiate it from a semantically based theory are that the deepest level of representations specifies the communicative intent primarily and semantic content secondarily. Thus, within this theory the language acquisition can easily be realized differently in emphasizing the role of the environment in producing such differences, as is most often the case in child language and not infrequently the case in adult language.

According to Vygotsky (1962), social interaction plays an important role of "shared language" in the development of thought and language. The term "shared language" refers to social interaction and can be best elucidated through the notion of "zone of proximal development". As one of the factors that affects the English speaking accuracy of Aeta Magbuken students is community related factors wherein learning resources, lifestyle and exposure to media really affects their language acquisition. Thus, there must be sufficient learning resources in the

community to motivate AetaMagbuken students to change their way of thinking about language acquisition and they will be able to expose to some Medias that will help them to develop the target language. Interaction can occur through cooperative learning activities while providing opportunities to develop linguistic and communicative competence.

The Monitor and Affective Filter Theory of Cummins (1994) support this study and the preceding findings of Krashen. The monitor is a kind of internal grammatical “editing” function that regulates or alters the way that a person uses the second language verbally. This phenomenon is related in some cases to how confident or inhibited a learner feels (e.g., he/she doesn’t care about making grammatical errors and just wants to communicate or cares so much about making mistakes that he/she is afraid to speak). Affective filter is an emotional-mental block or barrier that interferes with or prevents input from reaching the cognitive and language centers of the brain. This symbolic “wall” may be caused by learner anxiety, stress, and lack of self-confidence or motivation, physical discomfort, hunger, etc. Learners with a low affective filter will not only be efficient language acquirers of the comprehensible input they receive. They are also more likely to interact with others, unembarrassed by making mistakes for example, and thus increase the amount of that input.

Firstly, if teachers make their classroom instruction comprehensible, then not only will the ESL students learn the subject content but they will be acquiring English at the same time. All teachers of non-native English students should regard themselves as teachers of language too. Secondly, ESL students are often anxious in mainstream classes. Teachers should seek ways to reduce the students' affective filter in order that they can profit from the comprehensible input they receive. One of the factors that affects the English speaking proficiency of AetaMagbuken in terms of grammar is the student related factors wherein initiative, self-esteem and exposure to English

Literature influence their oral proficiency. Thus, AetaMagbuken students' personality and attitude greatly affect their acquisition of English Oral Accuracy in terms of grammar.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 presented the paradigm of the study.

The first frame presented the independent variables which pertain to the community-related factors, teacher related factors and student related factors.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

It also included community-related factors in terms of learning resources, lifestyle and exposure to media; teacher-related factors in terms of teaching strategies and attitudes toward Magbuken students; and student-related factors in terms of initiative, self-esteem and exposure to English Literature.

The second frame contained the dependent variable which is the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken high school students as reflected in their use of prepositions/prepositional phrases, verb tenses, simple sentence construction, and subject-verb agreement.

The researchers postulated that the independent variable greatly influenced the dependent variable and hence, significance relationships exist between the two.

Statement of the problem

The general problem of the study was how can school, community, teacher and students related factors affect the Oral English Accuracy of Aeta Magbuken high school students of Limay National High School?

Specifically, the research sought answers to the following questions:

1. How can community related factors be described in terms of:

1.1 learning resources;

1.2 lifestyle; and

1.3 exposure to media?

2. How can teacher related factors be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 teaching strategies; and
 - 2.2 attitudes toward Magbuken students?
3. How can students' related factors be described in terms of:
 - 3.1 initiative;
 - 3.2 self-esteem; and
 - 3.3 exposure to English literature?
4. What is the Oral English Accuracy of Aeta Magbuken high school students?
 - 4.1 use of prepositions/prepositional phrases;
 - 4.2 verb tenses (simple present, past and future;
 - 4.3 sentence construction; and
 - 4.4 subject-verb agreement?
5. Is there any significant relationship between community related factors and the Oral English Accuracy of the students?
6. Is there any significant relationship between teacher related factors and the Oral English Accuracy of the students?
7. Is there any significant relationship between students' related factors and their Oral English Accuracy?

Significance of the study

This study is deemed significant to the following:

Teachers. The findings of this study may reveal the attitudes of the teachers affecting the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students. This may show them how these attitudes affect and hinder the students' acquisition of the second language so that they can think of possible solutions in order to assess it closely. Another thing, this study will help them to identify the needs of the students especially the Aeta Magbuken students in learning the L2. This will give them indications on why these students are having problems in using the English language accurately. This may aid them to improve in their expertise not only in the preparation of the lesson but also in different drills and activities designed. Such expertise may enable them to modify the teaching strategies in implementing English speaking instruction that are appropriate to meet the needs of the students. Furthermore, the findings of the study may also help teachers design learning interventions that can support the English language instruction effective and efficient. These interventions may help the students develop and master the tasks expected at their age and level.

Students. This study may be most significant to the Aeta Magbuken students for they are the beneficiary of this research whose welfare is to help them identify their problem in their speaking accuracy towards English language. Identification of the strength and weaknesses of the level of accuracy in speaking the language, in effect, bring about some improvements. This may help them to fully understand and realize the benefits of learning the English language. It will inform them the factors that affect their oral English accuracy and they will also discover some ways to handle it. Thus, desired changes will lead the way to be better in terms of speaking the L2. They will develop their confidence in using the language and will be motivated to learn it. Moreover, the findings of the study would also identify the difficulties of the students in terms of speaking the language so that appropriate assessments can be done and interventions can be made to address the problems.

Curriculum Planners. The findings of this study can be used as a starting point in planning, organizing, constructing, developing and enriching the curriculum materials for enhancing the oral English accuracy of the Kinaragan Aeta students. This may show them the problems in the curriculum that needs to be revised or changed so some development in the curriculum will be made and everyone will be benefited. This research may help the curriculum planners in designing measures or interventions by way of the policies to improve the English speaking accuracy of the children and possible ways to address their needs. The findings of this research will serve as an evidence and significant basis for the policy makers to address inconsistencies of the English speaking accuracy of the students.

Future Researchers. The study focuses on the level of English speaking accuracy of the Kinaragan Aetas which will serve as basis for future researchers who will embark the same study through utilization of other variables not used in this research. This research has the ultimate goal of partaking new information about measuring the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken students with those who are interested. This may show them the various factors affecting the oral English accuracy and the possible assessments possibly used to assess it. This may also give them an idea in conducting proper experimentation and correct procedures in order to meet their goals for their research. Furthermore, researchers might find relevant ideas and information that can compare and add to their research to help them accomplish their recent study.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study aimed to identify the factors affecting the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken high school students in the Municipality of Limay. The respondents of the study were

composed of 15 Aeta Magbuken students of Limay National High School who were selected using purposive sampling technique.

Explicitly, it evaluated the community-related factors in terms of learning resources, lifestyle and exposure to media. Besides, it identified the teacher-related factors in terms of teaching strategies and attitude towards Aeta Magbuken high school students. Furthermore, it distinguished the student-related factors in terms of initiative, self-esteem and exposure to English literature. Likewise, the students' oral English accuracy was assessed in terms of use of prepositions/prepositional phrases, use of verb tenses (simple present, past and future), sentence construction and subject-verb agreement. However, this study was only limited towards assessing oral English accuracy in terms of abovementioned four specific grammatical areas and intentionally focused on basics to effectively identify the significant relationships of each related factors given.

The data were organized through oral interview and survey questionnaire. The data were organized and processed through the PASW Statistics Version 18 (previously known as SPSS). Mean or average was utilized to present the result of the survey-questionnaires of the abovementioned factors. To test the significant relationships of the factors that affect the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken students, Pearson Correlation (r) and Coefficient of determination (t -test) was used. The study was delimited among the Aeta Magbuken students who have been subjected to oral English accuracy test.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presented the methods and techniques, population and sample, research instrument, construction and validation of instruments, data gathering procedure and the statistical treatment used in the study.

Methods and Techniques of the Study

This study aimed to identify some related factors that affected the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken students of Limay National High School using the descriptive correlational type of research.

According to Glass & Hopkins (2006), any scientific process begins with description, based on observation, of an event or events, from which theories may later be developed to explain the observations. It describes the characteristic of a population being studied, the characteristics used to describe the situation or population as usually some kind of categorical scheme also known as descriptive categories as it seeks to describe the current status of an identified variable. These research projects are designed to provide systematic information about a phenomenon; as well as, Correlation research attempts to determine the extent of a relationship between two or more variables using statistical data. A correlation is simply defined as a relationship between two variables. The whole purpose of using correlations in research is to figure out which variables are connected. This simple definition is the basis of several statistical tests that result in a correlation coefficient, defined as a numerical representation of the strength and direction of a relationship.

According to Kowalczyk (2015), correlation research is looking for variables that seem to interact with each other, so that when you can see one changing, you have an idea of how the other will change. This often entails the researcher using variables that they can't control. For example, a researcher may be interested in studying the preference for ice cream based on age. If we cannot assign age, doesn't mean we have to scrap the whole correlation.

According to Peswell (2007), it is a design which uses some form of correlation to describe the data, but does not seek to find whether it is a statistically significant relationship, e.g., I run a small pilot study with 10 people and record their age and whether they like tattoos (scaled from 1= no to 7 a lot), I get a negative correlation of 0.4. I use this descriptively to decide there is something to investigate, and then use an inferential correlation with a better sized more representative sample to see if there is a significant relationship between the two variables.

Population of the Students

Limay National High School served as the research locale. The respondents of the study were the 15 Aeta Magbuken students from different grade levels during the School Year 2016-2017.

Table 1
Population and Sample of the Study

	J u n i o r H i g h S c h o o l							
	G r a d e 7		G r a d e 8		G r a d e 9		G r a d e 10	
	P o p .	Samp.	P o p	Samp.	P o p .	Samp.	P o p .	Samp.
	4	4	5	5	3	3	3	3
Total		4		5		3		3

Purposive sampling technique was used to determine the population of the student-respondents. The level of confidence used was 95 percent with $\pm 5\%$ margin of error.

Research Instruments

The primary research instrument in this study was the survey-questionnaire. Likewise, an interview was used to examine relevant documents that could help generate facts and information for the study.

Therefore, sets of survey-questionnaires were prepared for the student and teacher-respondents. This was divided into three parts: community-related factors in terms of learning resources, lifestyle and exposure to media. It was rated through providing survey questionnaires to be answered by the respondents to know the availability of the learning resources, their way of living and how exposure to media affects their acquisition of the L2; student-related factors in terms of initiative, self-esteem and exposure to English Literature. It was done through personal interview and having them answer the survey questionnaires; and teacher-related factors in terms of teaching strategies and attitudes towards Magbuken students. This was rated through providing the teacher respondents a survey questionnaire to answer focused on their teaching strategies and attitude towards Aeta Magbuken students.

Construction and Validation of Instruments

The survey-questionnaires were constructed using items from iRubrics, theses and dissertation in various speaking problems. Other sources of survey questionnaires came from formal and informal interviews and observations.

For evaluating the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken, the questionnaire was applied which composed of three parts and an oral interview composed of five questions.

The reliability and validity of the questionnaire was determined using experts' validation. The questionnaire was a decomposition procedure that identifies the underlying relationships that exists within a set of variables. It helped to break down large information into small and manageable parts. Using the procedure, it was found that the questionnaires measure 3 related factors affecting the speaking accuracy of the respondents. However, it only explains 45% of the variability of the students and 19% explain on the variability of the school, while 20% explains on the variability of the teacher, and the 16% explains on the variability of community.

On the other hand, this study was used to pursue the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students which was reflected on the findings of the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the survey-questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, a letter of validation was secured and approved by the Office of the Principal of Limay National High School. After securing the necessary permit, a letter was sent to the teachers of Limay National High School which is asking for the permission to administer the survey-questionnaires among the selected students of various levels.

After the necessary approval has been acquired, one week was allotted for distribution of the survey-questionnaires as well as the retrieval of such. This span of time would be enough to facilitate the distribution and retrieval of the survey. Finally, after all the data were retrieved, these were tabulated, analyzed and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data were organized and processed through the PASW Statistics Version 18 (previously known as SPSS).

Mean or average was utilized to present the result of the survey-questionnaires of the factors affecting the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken in terms of community-related factors (learning resources, lifestyle, exposure to media), teacher-related factors (teaching strategies, attitudes toward Magbuken students), and student-related factors (initiative, self-esteem, exposure to English literature).

To test the significant relationship of the factors that affects the oral English Accuracy of Aeta Magbuken students, Pearson Correlation (r) and Coefficient of determination (t -test) was used. For ease of interpretation, this study adopted the Simplified Approach to Statistics as recommended by **Ma. Felisa D. Angeles et. Al., Mutya Publishing House, Inc. (2005)**

± 1.00	Perfect Positive (Negative) Correlation
$\pm 0.91 - \pm 0.99$	Very High Positive (Negative) Correlation
$\pm 0.71 - \pm 0.90$	High Positive (Negative) Correlation
$\pm 0.51 - \pm 0.70$	Moderately Positive (Negative) Correlation
$\pm 0.31 - \pm 0.50$	Low Positive (Negative) Correlation
$\pm 0.01 - \pm 0.31$	Negligible Positive (Negative) Correlation

On the other hand, the rejection or acceptance of a null hypothesis was based on 5% level of significance. As PASW Statistics software readily provided the significance level of a test, the output significance was compared to 0.05 level to determine the significance of that value. If the value is less than or equal to 0.05, then there is a significant difference or relationship; hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. Otherwise, there is no significant difference or relationship and the null hypothesis was accepted.

RESULTS

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, & INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the results of the analysis and interpretation of data relevant to the study on the effect of community, teacher and student related factors on the Oral English Accuracy of Aeta Magbuken high school students of Limay National High School during S.Y. 2016-2017. This chapter also involves discussing the findings in relation to other studies conducted by other researchers on similar subject.

To have a strong and broad presentation of findings, this chapter is subdivided into five (5) parts parallel to the specific questions enumerated in the Statement of the Problem in Chapter I of this study.

Part I describes the possible factors in the community. This includes its learning resources, lifestyle and exposure to media.

Part II presents the possible teacher related factors. This comprises the teaching strategies and the attitudes of the teachers toward Magbuken students.

Part III explains the student related factors. It discusses the students' initiative, self-esteem and exposure to English literature.

Part IV shows the Oral English Accuracy of Aeta Magbuken students. They are tested in terms of the use of prepositions/prepositional phrases, verb tenses (e.g. simple present, past and future), sentence construction, and subject-verb agreement.

Part V explains the significant relationship between the community, teacher and student related factors towards the Oral English Accuracy of the students.

Part I. Community Related Factors

The following tables contain the different community related factors such as learning resources, lifestyle and exposure to media.

Table 2 presents the learning resources available for the students.

Table 2.1
Learning Resources

Learning Resources	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Provision of public library services (reading room, chairs and tables, shelves, reference books, regular opening hours for the students in the community.)	1.87	Disagree
2. Availability of museums, nature centers and other places to explore that are unique to the community.	1.60	Disagree
3. Access to computers, telephones, guest chairs, and shelves in the community.	2.20	Disagree
4. Availability of computer shops/internet café	1.53	Disagree
5. Availability of textbooks, reference materials, manuals, guidelines provided for Aeta Magbuken students in the community.	2.47	Disagree
OVERALL MEAN	1.93	Disagree

Scale of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Available
3.50 – 4.49	Agree	Very Much Available
2.50 – 3.49	Undecided	Available
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Available
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Not Available

Data shows that the students disagree on the availability of learning resources in their community as indicated by the mean rating of 1.93. This means that the learning resources included in the questionnaire were sometimes available for the learners. The lowest mean of 1.53 was shown

for the availability of computer shops/internet café and the highest mean of 2.47 for the availability of textbooks, reference materials, manuals, guidelines provided for Aeta Magbuken students in the community both signifies a disagree equivalent. Also, this leads to a fact that these resources were sometimes available for the students.

Generally, the learning resources present in the community affect the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students as reflected in the overall mean of 1.93 or Disagree.

The findings supported the study of Knapp, C.E (1996) who stated that community resources enhance language learning include centers to visit (museums, libraries, nature centers, interactive science centers, aquaria, gardens and zoos), places to explore that are unique to the local school (a nearby creek, pond, city street or business), people in the community, or materials that can be borrowed or purchased. Changing the educational experiences of children by moving beyond the classroom walls can diversify the array of learning opportunities and connect school lessons with daily life and real problems. Children generally find interactive exhibits engaging. These exhibits can be appealing and effective tools for teaching English for generating a positive attitude toward learning this subject.

Table 3 shows the lifestyle in the community.

Table 2.2
Lifestyle in the Community

Lifestyle	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I speak English with my friends in the community	1.87	Disagree
2. I practice speaking English at home	2.73	Neutral
3. I think speaking English with other people increases my status.	3.00	Neutral
4. It is possible for an Aeta Magbuken student to express his or her feelings completely in English language.	3.27	Neutral

5. English language is more prestigious than my native language	2.13	Disagree
OVERALL MEAN	2.60	Neutral

Scale of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
3.50 – 4.49	Agree	Very Much Practiced
2.50 – 3.49	Undecided	Practiced
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Practiced
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Not Practiced

The table gives a clear data that speaking English with their friends in the community is sometimes practiced as per mean rating 1.87 is observed. Meanwhile, students were said to practice speaking English at home, having a perspective that speaking English with other people increases his status and the possibility for an Aeta Magbuken student to express his or her feelings completely in English language as indicated by mean ratings of 2.73,3.00 and 3.27, respectively.

Generally, the lifestyle of the Aeta Magbuken students somtimest affect the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students as reflected in the average mean of 2.60 or Undecided.

The finding is similar to the study of Wolfe (2007), ethnicity and culture impact every person in both overt and subtle ways. At a very young age, children develop their speaking skills and begin to construct meaning regarding the words they say. The theoretical reason is that the successful acquisition and use of a language variety in a community of speakers would be impossible if language were not systematic and rule-governed. If every speaker could make up his or her own words and rules for pronunciation and grammar, communication between different speakers would be virtually impossible.

Table 4 shows the exposure to media in the community.

Table 2.3

Exposure to Media

Exposure to media	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Availability of a TV set to be used for educational purposes	4.13	Agree
2. Availability of tape players for media and educational purposes	1.73	Disagree
3. Availability of CD/DVD players for media and educational purposes	2.07	Disagree
4. Availability of a functional LCD for educational purposes	1.00	Strongly Disagree
5. Availability of Computer Service for students	1.73	Disagree
OVERALL MEAN	2.10	Disagree

Scale of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Exposed
3.50 – 4.49	Agree	Very Much Exposed
2.50 – 3.49	Undecided	Exposed
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Exposed
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Not Exposed

It is very visible that the students were not exposed in the use of a functional LCD for educational purposes as mean rating observed is 1.00. Hence, this is far different for a very much exposure on TV set to be used for educational purposes, having a mean of 4.13. In total, the students' exposure to media in their community turned out to be sometimes exposed as obtained mean is 2.10.

Generally, exposure to media of the Aeta Magbuken students affect the learning of English language as reflected in the average mean of 2.1 or few.

The findings supported the study of (Locksley 2009) who stated that media has spread rapidly throughout the developing world, with increasing penetration of television CD/DVD, LCD and computers. Recent evidence indicates that this growing mass media can contribute significantly to socioeconomic and educational development. It can facilitate access to knowledge,

motivate beneficial changes in individual behaviors, and catalyze the process of social change in sectors such as health, agriculture.

Media are good investments and outcomes in education, without which the country will face demographic disaster in the form of a large, disillusioned and unproductive young population. The number of television sets almost tripled from 3.8 million in 2004 to 9 million in 2007. The national government has made attempt to explore the usefulness of CD/DVD, LCD, computers and television as adjuncts to the formal educational system. Regular access to and use of mass media outside of school may broaden the opportunity for children to absorb information, read and increase their cognitive skills. Willingham (2009) suggests that people learn abstract, new, and novel concepts more easily when they are presented in both verbal and visual form (Salomon, 1979). Other empirical research shows that visual media make concepts more accessible to a person than text media and help with later recall. In his research he asks a simple question to make his point, "Why do students remember everything that's on television and forget what we lecture?" – because visual media helps students retain concepts and ideas. He also notes the crucial role that technology plays for creating learning environments that extend the possibilities of one-way communication media, such as movies, documentaries, television shows and music into new areas that require interactive learning like visualizations and student-created content.

Part II. Teacher Related Factors

Table 5 shows the teaching strategies of the teachers.

Table 3.1

Teacher Factor in terms of Teaching Strategies

Teaching Strategies	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. When preparing my English lessons in speaking, I make sure that my lesson objectives will be targeted and will be applicable to my students who have multiple intelligences	3.17	Neutral
2. The most important thing that I should remember is that my students need to speak English as much as possible	2.50	Neutral
3. When I teach speaking, I make the grammar lessons the focal point of my instruction	3.17	Neutral
4. It is important that I focus on each student and choose those skills that are most important for him or her.	2.00	Disagree
5. In teaching speaking, I should plan lessons that involve more than just passive learning	2.17	Disagree
OVERALL MEAN	2.60	Neutral

Scale of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
3.50 – 4.49	Agree	Agree
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral	Undecided
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Disagree
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree

In terms of teaching strategies, data shows that the teachers were neutral, having an overall mean of 2.60, on the implementation of various strategies that will help the learners. Also, teachers disagree on two issues namely, the importance of focusing on each student and choose skills that is most important to him/her, and planning the lessons that involve more than just passive learning as mean achieved are 2.00 and 2.17, respectively.

Generally, the teachers' teaching strategies sometimes affect the learning of English language of the Aeta Magbuken students as reflected in the average mean of 2.60 or neutral.

The findings supported the study of Brown (2007) which points out that the quality of instruction is fundamental to student learning. In discussion about language teaching and learning, there is a depending and subordinating relationship between teaching and learning. Teaching

strategies play roles as guiding, facilitating learning, and encouraging the learner and setting the conditions for learning. According to Cook (2001), “the proof of teaching is in the learning”, and “all successful teaching depends upon learning.” Cook also states that there is no point in providing interesting, well prepared language lessons if students do not learn from them. Having a good understanding of how the learner learns will help teachers determine their philosophy of education, their teaching style, approach, methods, and classroom techniques. If the teachers rarely use visual materials such as cards, charts, and real objects in language teaching, the effectiveness of these visual aids to the students’ learning will not be targeted. To have effective teaching materials for the lessons, the teachers have to spend time seeking, designing, and selecting the appropriate teaching aids because “teachers play a key role in changes to teaching methodology and contribute to improvements in the quality of education, especially English as a foreign language teachers who have to meet the needs and standards of English as an international language” (Vo & Nguyen, 2010).

According to Elliot (2008), teachers tend to view speaking as the least useful of the basic language skills and therefore they generally sacrifice teaching speaking in order to spend valuable class time on other areas of language. Or maybe, teachers feel justified neglecting speaking believing that for non-native language learners, it is more difficult to attain target language speaking skills than other facets of second language acquisition. Teachers just do not have the background or tools to properly teach speaking and therefore it is disregarded.

Table 6 shows the attitude of the teachers towards Magbuken Students.

Table 3.2

Teacher Factor in terms of Attitude toward Magbuken Students

Attitude	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. When I encounter several verbal communication problems that confine comprehension of instructional material and effective discussions in the classroom, I do not use strategies that enhance and maintain verbal communication in the classroom.	3.50	Agree
2. When I teach a racially diverse class, often during class discussions related to racial issues, friction occurs which leads to hostility among the students, I cannot create a learning environment where my students can discuss these issues without being racially biased.	2.33	Disagree
3. When I am teaching a class consisting of an approximately equal number of male and female students and notice that many girls and boys firmly reject activities, role playing, and academic subjects that they believe are inconsistent with their gender schemata, I am not certain that I can develop a classroom environment that encourages my students to adhere to nontraditional gender stereotypes.	3.67	Agree
4. When I am teaching a class with students from diverse backgrounds that are at risk for academic failure and I notice that these students show signs of low self-esteem, disinterest in school activities, and at times exhibit disruptive behavior, I am not certain that I can develop culturally-related context activities to encourage my students to participate in academic classroom tasks.	1.50	Disagree
5. When I am teaching a class with students from various ethnic backgrounds with different traditions, customs, conventions, values, and religious beliefs and I notice that some of my students have trouble tolerating one another's differences, I am not certain that I can provide my students with opportunities that foster awareness and appreciation of cultural differences.	2.00	Disagree
OVERALL MEAN	2.60	Neutral

Scale of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
3.50 – 4.49	Agree	Agree
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral	Undecided
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Disagree
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree

The attitude of the teachers towards the Magbuken Aeta students was Undecided as overall mean rating falls to 2.60 (Neutral). Examining the items included, teachers agree on two things, that is, when I encounter several verbal communication problems that confine comprehension of

instructional material and effective discussions in the classroom, I do not use strategies that enhance and maintain verbal communication in the classroom, and when I am teaching a class consisting of an approximately equal number of male and female students and notice that many girls and boys firmly reject activities, role playing, and academic subjects that they believe are inconsistent with their gender schemata, I am not certain that I can develop a classroom environment that encourages my students to adhere to nontraditional gender stereotypes, as means yielded at 3.50 and 3.67, respectively.

The finding supported the study of (Al-Magid 2006) that teachers' attitudes sometimes influenced the implementation of Communicative Approach in the ESL classrooms. Teachers, whose attitudes are positive, are able to mediate between what the theory calls for and the classrooms actually require and allow, due to different situations in the teaching environment. The influence of teachers' attitudes towards how effectively they apply it is certain but not necessarily conclusive because there are number of variables that have to be considered in this regard, such as individual differences, the role of educational policy-making authority and of parents and society as well as teachers' competencies. It should be stressed that teachers are not necessarily aware of their own attitudes as they merely follow instructions without considering whether prescribed procedures are the most appropriate for the task in hand.

Teachers' attitudes, while critical for the effective implementation of the Communicative Approach, are only one component of this process and must be considered in relation to other variables such as individual factors that contribute to its effective implementation.

Part III. Student Related Factors

Table 9 shows the student related factors in terms of initiative.

Table 4.1
Students' Initiative

Initiative	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Studying English is important because it will make me more educated	2.07	Disagree
2. I put off my English homework as much as possible	2.73	Neutral
3. I look forward to studying more English in the future	1.47	Strongly Disagree
4. I do not like studying English	3.67	Agree
5. When I hear my classmate speaking English well, I like to practice speaking with him/her	2.60	Neutral
OVERALL MEAN	2.51	Neutral

Scale of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
3.50 – 4.49	Agree	Very Much Observed
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral	Observed
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Observed
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Not Observed

By and large, the initiative of the students in oral English is observed with an overall mean of 2.51. However, data shows that students strongly disagree on looking forward to study more English in the future. This was indicated by the lowest mean rating of 1.47. This was supported by the highest mean of 3.67 for item 4 which states that I do not like studying English and this is very much observed to the students.

The findings negated the study of (Rivers 2009) stated that students' initiative does not affect second language fluency and accuracy because how can they be able to show initiative if the participation of the students given by the teacher is low or uneven. In a large group, each student will have very little talking time because only one participant can talk at a time so that the others can hear him/her.

Another thing Rivers believes that the learners have nothing to express or lacking initiative to express because the teacher had chosen a topic which is not suitable for him or about which he knows very little.

Table 4.2 presents the student related factors in terms of self-esteem.

Table 4.2
Students' Self-Esteem

Self-esteem	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I feel proud when studying English language	1.20	Strongly Disagree
2. Speaking English anywhere makes me feel worried	4.00	Agree
3. Studying English helps me to have good relationships with friends	1.47	Strongly Disagree
4. I think I cannot talk with others in English language because I might commit grammatical errors	4.67	Strongly Agree
5. Studying English makes me have more confidence in expressing myself	1.67	Disagree
OVERALL MEAN	2.60	Neutral

Scale of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
3.50 – 4.49	Agree	Very Much Observed
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral	Observed
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Observed
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Not Observed

In terms of the students' self-esteem, the table shows a neutral rating of 2.60. Students strongly disagree on being proud when studying the English language, mean is 1.20. Also, students strongly agree on the 4th questions which is I think I cannot talk with others in English language because I might commit grammatical errors, with a mean rating of 4.67.

Generally, the attitudes of the teachers toward Magbuken students sometimes affect the learning of English language of the Aeta Magbuken students as reflected in the average mean of 2.60 or neutral..

The finding supported the study of Al-Magid (2006) that teachers' attitudes sometimes influenced the implementation of Communicative Approach in the ESL classrooms. Teachers, whose attitudes are positive, are able to mediate between what the theory calls for and the classrooms actually require and allow, due to different situations in the teaching environment. The influence of teachers' attitudes towards how effectively they apply it is certain but not necessarily conclusive because there are number of variables that have to be considered in this regard, such as individual differences, the role of educational policy-making authority and of parents and society as well as teachers' competencies. It should be stressed that teachers are not necessarily aware of their own attitudes as they merely follow instructions without considering whether prescribed procedures are the most appropriate for the task in hand.

Teachers' attitudes, while critical for the effective implementation of the Communicative Approach, are only one component of this process and must be considered in relation to other variables such as individual factors that contribute to its effective implementation.

Table 4.3 presents the student related factors in terms of exposure to English Literature.

Table 4.3

Students' Exposure to English Literature

Exposure to Literature	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I simply quote the textbooks and do not really communicate myself when speaking in class	3.27	Neutral
2. I am interested in reading only English textbooks for my study but no other English text (e.g. magazine, newspapers).	3.00	Neutral

3. I am interested in furthering my critical thinking through enriching my knowledge in literature	4.13	Agree
4. Reading short stories makes me knowledgeable	4.00	Agree
5. I mainly focus on reading texts in mother tongue than English	3.80	Agree
OVERALL MEAN	3.64	Agree

Scale of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Exposed
3.50 – 4.49	Agree	Very Much Exposed
2.50 – 3.49	Undecided	Exposed
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Exposed
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Not Exposed

The table gives that the overall mean rating of 3.64 means that the students are very much exposed to English Literature. Students are exposed in quoting the textbooks and do not really communicate when speaking in class (mean = 3.27) and interested in reading only English textbooks for study but no other English text (e.g. magazine, newspapers), as mean rating obtained is 3.00. However, students are interested in furthering their critical thinking through enriching their knowledge in literature as highest mean of 4.13 is observed.

Generally, initiative of the Aeta Magbuken students affect the learning of English language as reflected in the average mean of 2.50 or rarely.

The findings contrasted the study of (McGregor 2007) who stated that where there is a little reading, there will be little language learning. Thus, it is clear that reading books, magazines and other reading materials, not only develop writing skill but also helps in improving speaking with speech fluency and sentence accuracy. It is also believed that the students who read a lot are likely speak well.

An authentic text is one that possesses an intrinsically communicative quality. With such advantages of reading literature in improving and developing language skills, particularly

speaking skills, this paper investigates the relationship between reading habit and improving speaking proficiency as reading enriches much needed vocabulary in EFL context and also offers practical language in use with interesting examples from various genres.

Part IV. Oral English Accuracy of Aeta Magbuken High School Students

Table 12 shows the Oral English Accuracy of Aeta MAGbuken High School Students in terms of the use of prepositions/prepositional phrases, verb tenses (simple present, past and future), sentence construction and subject-verb agreement.

Table 5

Oral English Accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken Students in Terms of Use of Prepositions/ Prepositional Phrase

Oral Accuracy	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
I. Use of Prepositions	1.53	Meets Expectation
1. Content	1.73	Meets Expectation
2. Parallelism	1.40	Needs Improvement
3. Structure	1.47	Needs Improvement
II. Verb Tenses	1.31	Needs Improvement
1. Simple Present Tense	1.67	Meets Expectation
2. Simple Past Tense	1.06	Needs Improvement
3. Simple Future Tense	1.20	Needs Improvement
III. Simple Sentence Construction	1.40	Needs Improvement
1. Content	1.73	Meets Expectation
2. Order	1.20	Needs Improvement
3. Clarity	1.27	Needs Improvement
IV. Subject-Verb Agreement	1.20	Needs Improvement
1. Rule 1,2,3	1.60	Meets Expectation
2. Rule 4, 5, 6	1.00	Needs Improvement
3. Rule 7, 8, 9, 10	1.00	Needs Improvement

OVERALL MEAN	1.36	Needs Improvement
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Scale of Means	Descriptive Equivalent
2.50 – 3.00	Exceeds Expectation
1.50 – 2.49	Meets Expectation
1.00 – 1.49	Needs Improvement

In testing the Oral English Accuracy of the students, the following results were obtained. The use of prepositions/prepositional phrases Meets Expectations with the mean rating of 1.53. However, verb tenses which involves simple present, past and future turned out for the need of improvement as mean rating yields 1.31. But, the use of simple present tense meets the required expectations as per mean rating of 1.67 is obtained. Likewise, sentence construction also calls for the need of improvement, having a mean rating of 1.40. To add, its content meets the expectations included in the study. As per subject-verb agreement, the mean of 1.20 indicates the need for improvement. This was supported by the man rating of 1.00, the lowest rating for all, for Rules 4-10. Overall, the mean rating of 1.36 is observed which means that the learners needs to improve on the criteria included in this study.

The findings supported the study of Krashen (1982), one major grammar error observed in both students' speech and writing is the prepositional error. State those errors are the flawed side of a learner's speech or writing. An error is any deviation from a selected norm of language performance, no matter what the characteristics or causes might be. The problems of the Filipinos with the preposition may be grouped into three: 1) using incorrect (unidiomatic) preposition; 2) non-use of a preposition when one is needed; 3) using a preposition when none is needed.

The findings proved the study of Otavio (2011), sentences look mature and contain clear messages but are wrong because they violate the rule of subject-verb agreement, if you want to assess the extent to which your students have truly internalized subject/verb agreement rules, you

must test how consistently they are getting the third persons 'right in spontaneous communication, across a range of verbs as isolated instances probably would not tell much.

Part V. Significant Relationship Between Community, Teacher and Student Related Factors and the Oral English Accuracy of the Students

Table 13 reveals the computation for identifying the significant relationship between the community-related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students.

Table 6

Pearson R Test Output for the Relationship Between the Community-Related Factors and the Oral English Accuracy of the Students.

Community Related Factors	R	Qualitative Interpretation	t value	Decision
Learning Resources	0.95	Very High Positive Correlation	10.92	Reject Ho
Lifestyle	0.97	Very High Positive Correlation	13.32	Reject Ho
Exposure to Media	0.94	Very High Positive Correlation	9.75	Reject Ho

Scales

± 1.00

± 0.91 - ± 0.99

± 0.71 - ± 0.90

± 0.51 - ± 0.70

± 0.31 - ± 0.50

± 0.01 - ± 0.31

Interpretation

Perfect Positive (Negative) Correlation

Very High Positive (Negative) Correlation

High Positive (Negative) Correlation

Moderately Positive (Negative) Correlation

Low Positive (Negative) Correlation

Negligible Positive (Negative) Correlation

All community related factors such as learning resources, lifestyle and exposure to media obtain a Very High Positive Correlation(relationship) towards the Oral English Accuracy of the students, means were 0.95. 0.97 and 0.94, respectively. These mean that as these factors develop or grow the most likely that the students become accurate in their Oral English skills.

Thus, such results lead to the rejection of the null hypotheses of the study.

The community related factors greatly influenced the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students. First is Learning Resources. Students need resources such as libraries, mini parks, museums, and other sources of information to enhance their language skills and for them to acquire the knowledge they need. It is important that students are exposed to different resources so that they will not just stick on only one source. The findings supported the study of Knapp, C.E (1996) who stated that community resources enhance language learning include centers to visit (museums, libraries, nature centers, interactive science centers, aquaria, gardens and zoos), places to explore that are unique to the local school (a nearby creek, pond, city street or business), people in the community, or materials that can be borrowed or purchased. Changing the educational experiences of children by moving beyond the classroom walls can diversify the array of learning opportunities and connect school lessons with daily life and real problems. Children generally find interactive exhibits engaging. These exhibits can be appealing and effective tools for teaching English for generating a positive attitude toward learning this subject. The richness of the community resources is apparent from the number and diversity. Imagination and creativity in using community resources can help students connect school English subject with applications in the community, as well as helping students better learn basic concepts. Children from many sources, in a range of different ways, and for a variety of purposes. Taking students to a library,

museum or out of the school grounds, exposing them to innovative materials, or inviting guests who can give unique insights are a few ways to increase their learning experiences.

Secondly, Lifestyle. The Aeta Magbuken students' lifestyle also contributes to their acquisition of the second language. Constant practice of speaking English inside and outside the classroom enhance their ability to communicate with others using the target language. The findings supported study of (Hymes 1973) who stated that the systematic nature of language as used by the members of particular speech communities rather than to pass (prescriptive) judgments about how well they speak or how they should or should not be using their language. The study of people's attitudes towards one variety or another is an interesting sub field of linguistics, one, which can help us to understand the social distribution of dialects or the direction of language change, and one, which can be helpful in formulating policy about which varieties to use in the schools and community.

The theoretical reason is that the successful acquisition and use of a language variety in a community of speakers would be impossible if language were not systematic and rule-governed. If every speaker could make up his or her own words and rules for pronunciation and grammar, communication between different speakers would be virtually impossible.

Lastly, Exposure to Media. Media exposure also influenced the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students. It will make them understand the English language in a more creative and more interactive way. There are different types of media that are being used nowadays. Media are being used by the teachers to facilitate learning and to deliver their lessons easily. The findings supported the study of (Locksley 2009) who stated that media has spread rapidly throughout the developing world, with increasing penetration of television CD/DVD, LCD and computers. Recent evidence indicates that this growing mass media can contribute significantly to socioeconomic and

educational development. It can facilitate access to knowledge, motivate beneficial changes in individual behaviors, and catalyze the process of social change in sectors such as health, agriculture. Media are good investments and outcomes in education, without which the country will face demographic disaster in the form of a large, disillusioned and unproductive young population. The number of television sets almost tripled from 3.8 million in 2004 to 9 million in 2007. The national government has made attempt to explore the usefulness of CD/DVD, LCD, computers and television as adjuncts to the formal educational system. Regular access to and use of mass media outside of school may broaden the opportunity for children to absorb information, read and increase their cognitive skills.

Table 14 reveals the computation for identifying the significant relationship between the teacher-related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students.

Table 7

Pearson R Test Output for the Relationship Between the Teacher-Related Factors and the Oral English Accuracy of the Students.

Teacher Related Factors	R	Qualitative Interpretation	t value	Decision
Teaching Strategies	0.97	Very High Positive Correlation	7.53	Reject Ho
Attitudes towards Magbuken Students	0.98	Very High Positive Correlation	9.86	Reject Ho

Scales

± 1.00

Interpretation

Perfect Positive (Negative) Correlation

$\pm 0.91 - \pm 0.99$	Very High Positive (Negative) Correlation
$\pm 0.71 - \pm 0.90$	High Positive (Negative) Correlation
$\pm 0.51 - \pm 0.70$	Moderately Positive (Negative) Correlation
$\pm 0.31 - \pm 0.50$	Low Positive (Negative) Correlation
$\pm 0.01 - \pm 0.31$	Negligible Positive (Negative) Correlation

Data presents a Very High Positive Correlation (Relationship) between the teacher-related factors and Oral English Accuracy of the students, having a mean of 0.97 and 0.98. These mean that as the teachers' strategies and attitude toward the students become high, the greater it helps the students to become more accurate in oral English. With this, the rejection of the null hypothesis is observed.

The teacher related factors in terms of Teaching Strategies and Attitude towards Aeta Magbuken students affect the development of the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken students. The strategies and techniques that the teachers are using contributes to the learning and acquisition of the English language. Teachers who are using English as their medium of instruction influenced the students to speak English in class. The findings supported the study of Brown (2007) which points out that the quality of instruction is fundamental to student learning. In discussion about language teaching and learning, there is a depending and subordinating relationship between teaching and learning. Teaching strategies play roles as guiding, facilitating learning, and encouraging the learner and setting the conditions for learning. According to Cook (2001), "the proof of teaching is in the learning", and "all successful teaching depends upon learning," Cook also states that there is no point in providing interesting, well prepared language lessons if students do not learn from them. Having a good understanding of how the learner learns will help teachers determine their philosophy of education, their teaching style, approach, methods,

and classroom techniques. If the teachers rarely use visual materials such as cards, charts, and real objects in language teaching, the effectiveness of these visual aids to the students' learning will not be targeted. To have effective teaching materials for the lessons, the teachers have to spend time seeking, designing, and selecting the appropriate teaching aids because "teachers play a key role in changes to teaching methodology and contribute to improvements in the quality of education, especially English as a foreign language teachers who have to meet the needs and standards of English as an international language" (Vo & Nguyen, 2010).

In addition, the teachers' attitudes also affects the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students. How the teachers treat their students also change the students' perception about learning the target language. The findings supported the study of (Al-Magid 2006) that teachers' attitudes sometimes influenced the implementation of Communicative Approach in the ESL classrooms. Teachers, whose attitudes are positive, are able to mediate between what the theory calls for and the classrooms actually require and allow, due to different situations in the teaching environment. The influence of teachers' attitudes towards how effectively they apply it is certain but not necessarily conclusive because there are number of variables that have to be considered in this regard, such as individual differences, the role of educational policy-making authority and of parents and society as well as teachers' competencies. It should be stressed that teachers are not necessarily aware of their own attitudes as they merely follow instructions without considering whether prescribed procedures are the most appropriate for the task in hand. Teachers' attitudes, while critical for the effective implementation of the Communicative Approach, are only one component of this process and must be considered in relation to other variables such as individual factors that contribute to its effective implementation.

Table 15 reveals the computation for identifying the significant relationship between the student-related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students.

Table 8

Pearson R Test Output for the Relationship Between the Student Related Factors and the Oral English Accuracy of the Students.

Student Related Factors	R	Qualitative Interpretation	t value	Decision
Initiative	0.95	Very High Positive Correlation	10.48	Reject Ho
Self-esteem	0.97	Very High Positive Correlation	14.64	Reject Ho
Exposure to English Literature	0.97	Very High Positive Correlation	14.39	Reject Ho

Scales

Interpretation

± 1.00

Perfect Positive (Negative) Correlation

± 0.91 - ± 0.99

Very High Positive (Negative) Correlation

± 0.71 - ± 0.90

High Positive (Negative) Correlation

± 0.51 - ± 0.70

Moderately Positive (Negative) Correlation

± 0.31 - ± 0.50

Low Positive (Negative) Correlation

± 0.01 - ± 0.31

Negligible Positive (Negative) Correlation

Data shows that all student-related factors have a Very High Positive Correlation (Relationship) on the Oral English Accuracy of the Magbuken Aeta high school students, obtaining a mean rating of 0.95 and 0.97. This means that the students' initiative, self-esteem and exposure

definitely affects their accuracy on oral English. Also, the rejection of the null hypothesis was observed in this factor.

The student related factors in terms of Initiative and Self-esteem affects the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students, however, Exposure to Literature does not. The student's initiative towards learning and acquiring English influenced their speaking skills. Those students who are willing to acquire and learn the target language, becomes more confident to express their ideas, thoughts, and feelings using the English language. The findings supported the study of Navehebrahim (2011) stated that students' initiative affect second language acquisition because the participation of the students in the class gives them the chance to speak more and be more active in communicating with others. In a large group, each student will have a chance to talk because all of the participants can talk when their teacher told them to do so. By that, it can help not only one student but also the others to be heard by the teacher. Another thing, he believes that the learners have to express because the teacher had chosen a topic that are suitable for them or about which he knows.

Another is Self-esteem. Students are eager to learn a new language when they are motivated and they have the confidence to use it without any uncertainty. Acquisition of the second language will be possible if the students are willing to express their ideas, thoughts, and feelings confidently using the English language. It will boost their trust to their speaking skills and it will make them to be more expressive. This supports the findings of Tuan (2015) stated that the affective factors play a prominent role in the development of learner's oral performance. Whenever teachers tried to understand pupils' reluctance to speak in the classroom, students found them confronted with a psychological factor that prevented students from using their oral English. Pupils' responses were related to anxiety, poor self-esteem and lack of motivation. Spolsky (2008)

stated that only 5% of non-native speakers can achieve high level of speaking skills. This means that in order to arrive at an acceptable level of near communication, L2 learner must possess certain biological, cognitive, affective and socio-cultural factors. Affective variables are considered as inhibition, risk-taking, anxiety, extroversion/introversion, motivation and self-esteem.

On the other hand, Exposure to Literature does not have any significant relationship in the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students. Students are exposed to literature in school and it is up to them to not only read it but also use and apply it in real-life setting. The result supported the findings of Robby (2009) stated that the simple fact that passive input will only improve your English vocabulary. Moreover, you simply won't improve your spoken English skills through reading magazines, books and other reading texts because by reading something in English you do not exercise you're reading just imprinting itself in your mind to be used in speaking English later on. Maley (2008) stated that written English used in actual live conversations. Written English tends to be more formal and is not packed with phrasal verbs like everyday English.

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings

The general problem of the study was how can school, community, teacher and students related factors affect the oral English accuracy of Aeta Magbuken high school students of Limay National High School during academic year 2016-2017?

Specifically, the research sought answers to the following questions:

1. How can community related factors be described in terms of:

- 1.1 learning resources;
 - 1.2 lifestyle; and
 - 1.3 exposure to media?
2. How can teacher related factors be described in terms of:
- 2.1 teaching strategies; and
 - 2.2 attitudes toward Magbuken students?
3. How can students' related factors be described in terms of:
- 3.1 initiative;
 - 3.2 self-esteem; and
 - 3.3 exposure to English literature?
4. What is the Oral English Accuracy of Aeta Magbuken high school students?
- 4.1 use of prepositions/prepositional phrases;
 - 4.2 verb tenses (simple present, past and future;
 - 4.3 sentence construction; and
 - 4.4 subject-verb agreement?
5. Is there any significant relationship between community related factors and the Oral English Accuracy of the students?
6. Is there any significant relationship between teacher related factors and the Oral English Accuracy of the students?
7. Is there any significant relationship between students' related factors and their Oral English Accuracy?

This study aimed to identify the factors affecting the oral English accuracy of Kinaragan Aetas in the Municipality of Limay during the school year 2016-2017. The respondents of the

study were composed of 15 Aeta Magbuken students of Limay National High School who were selected using purposive sampling technique.

Explicitly, it evaluated the community related factors in terms of learning resources, lifestyle and exposure to media. Besides, it identified the teacher related factors in terms of teaching strategies and attitude towards Aeta Magbuken high school students. Furthermore, it distinguished the students' related factors in terms of initiative, self-esteem and exposure to English literature. Likewise, the students' oral English accuracy were assessed in terms of use of prepositions/prepositional phrases, use of verb tenses (simple present, past and future), sentence construction and subject-verb agreement. However, this study was only limited towards assessing oral English accuracy in terms of abovementioned four specific grammatical areas and intentionally focused on basics to effectively identify the significant relationships of each related factors given.

The data were organized through oral interview and survey questionnaire. The study was delimited among the Aeta Magbuken students who have been subjected to oral English accuracy test within school year 2016-2017.

Based on the data gathered, the following were the findings:

1. On the Community-Related Factors

- **Learning Resources**

The community-related factor in terms of learning resources present in the community affect the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as disagree.

- **Lifestyle**

The community-related factor in terms of lifestyle of the Aeta Magbuken students affects the oral English accuracy and was rated as neutral.

- **Exposure to media**

The community-related factor in terms of exposure to media affects the Oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as disagree.

2. On the Student-Related Factors

- **Initiative**

The student-related factor in terms of initiative affects the Oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as neutral.

- **Self-esteem**

The student-related factor in terms of self-esteem affects the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as neutral.

- **Exposure to Literature**

The student-related factor in terms of exposure to literature does not affect the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as agree.

3. On the Teacher-Related factors

- **Teaching Strategies**

The teacher-related factor in terms of teachers' teaching strategies affects the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and were rated as neutral.

- **Attitudes toward Aeta Magbuken students**

The teacher-related factor in terms of attitudes of the teachers does not affect the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as neutral.

4. On the English Accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken Students

- **Use of preposition**

The English accuracy in terms of use of prepositions affects the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as meets expectations.

- **Verb tenses**

The English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students in terms of use of verb tenses affects the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as needs improvement.

- **Simple sentence structure**

The English accuracy in terms of use of simple sentence structure affects the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as needs improvement.

- **Subject-verb agreement**

The English accuracy in terms of use of subject-verb agreement affects the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students and was rated as needs improvement.

5. On the Significant relationship between community related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students

It was revealed that there is significant relationship between the teacher- related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students.

6. On the Significant relationship between teacher related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students

It was revealed that there is significant relationship between the teacher- related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students.

7. On the Significant relationship between students' related factors and oral English accuracy of the students

The study revealed that there is significant relationship between the student- related factors and oral English Accuracy of the students.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The community related factors in terms of learning resources present in the community sometimes affect the oral English accuracy of the Aeta Magbuken students. Also, the lifestyle of the Aeta Magbuken students sometimes affects their oral English accuracy. Furthermore, the Aeta Magbuken students disagree that they are exposed to media which affects their oral English accuracy.
2. The student related factors in terms of initiative of the Aeta Magbuken students sometimes affect their oral English accuracy. In addition, their self-esteem also sometimes affect their

oral English accuracy. Moreover, the Aeta Magbuken students agree that they are exposed to literature which does not affect their oral English accuracy.

3. The Aeta Magbuken students agree that the teachers' teaching strategies affect their oral English accuracy. On the other hand, the attitudes of the teachers towards Aeta Magbuken students sometimes affect their oral English accuracy.
4. The Aeta Magbuken students meet the expectations in the use of prepositions, while needs improvement in the use of verb tenses, in the use of simple sentence structure, and in the use of subject-verb agreement which affects their oral English accuracy.
5. The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the community- related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students was rejected.
6. The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the teacher- related factors and the oral English accuracy of the students was rejected.
7. The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the student- related factors and oral English Accuracy of the students was rejected.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended:

1. The teachers are recommended to expose the students with community learning resources through having field trips in other community nearby that has learning resources present like museums, public mini library and nature parks. Through this, the teacher can help to reach out the students' need even those are not present in their community. To teachers, since the community of Aeta Magbuken students are lacking when it comes to media, they must expose the students to use different technologies like computer, laptop, LCD, DVD,

etc. The teachers must also let the students, especially the students to manipulate and use those media in class activities.

2. The teachers should create an English speaking environment by encouraging the students to use English in the classroom to make it a habit, letting them watch films or videos in English and the teachers should also use English in the classroom frequently so that the students have more exposure to the language.

The teachers should also identify the strategies that best meet their language learners' immediate needs, and they can explore students' reaction to their learning approaches for the second language. Moreover, they can use classroom research as a tool for showing the language learners that the teaching strategies in second language acquisition really work. Teachers should provide opportunities to increase verbal interaction in classroom activities to help ensure that students are exposed to as many different types of authentic language as possible and allow students opportunities to practice using the target language. Planning for more group and pair work during lessons would help to do this. The following strategies and techniques could be incorporated more into practice by teachers to further improve the language support given to learners:

- a. Thinking Time- Teachers should try to consciously allow at least five seconds of silence after asking a question to allow language learners more time to connect to what has been asked and provide all students with the opportunity to think and answer
- b. Elaborated input -Teachers need to consider the ways that they speak to students and try to repeat key instructions or points, paraphrase, use slower, clear speech and visual aids to help students better comprehend what is being said

c. Re-casts- If a student makes an error when speaking, the teacher should repeat what the student said providing the correct model without overtly drawing attention to the error

d. Questioning - Teachers should be trying to ask more open ended questions to their students and directing these questions to specific individuals to ensure all students have the opportunity to participate

e. Increase verbal interaction - Teachers should provide opportunities to increase verbal interaction in classroom activities to help ensure that students are exposed to as many different types of authentic language as possible and allow students opportunities to practice using the target language. Planning for more group and pair work during lessons would help to do this. Regarding the attitude towards Aeta students, the EFL teachers are recommended to create an encouraging atmosphere in the English classes to promote the Aeta students' positive attitudes towards English. They should also motivate the Aeta students to learn English, highlighting its importance. This can be achieved by implementing the appropriate methods and activities of teaching English effectively. Furthermore, they should integrate up-to-date materials and supplementary resources in addition to the English text books. This can help them capture students' attention to learn English successfully.

3. The teacher should give the students more opportunity of collaborative learning by means of pair or group discussion to voice out their opinions with increased confidence when speaking L2. Having daily conversation, students experience a greater sense of ability and confidence to speak English. In this case, when students have the confidence to speak the language they can now have the initiative to speak English without hesitation. The teachers

should first improve the performance conditions by giving their students time to prepare for a speaking task, teaching the students how to use mind map to generate ideas and giving students enough time to perform their tasks. Teachers should help their students overcome inhibition and shyness by having friendly, helpful and cooperative behaviors to make students feel comfortable when speaking in the class, reminding students not to worry about making mistakes and giving them clear instructions and sufficient guidance. Teachers should also personalize and simplify the topics in the textbook to make them easier, more interesting and relevant to their lives. They should decide carefully when and how to correct the students' mistakes so that the students are not fearful of making mistakes and the flow of the students' conversation is not destroyed. In addition, they should also encourage students to participate in speaking activities. Finally, the teachers should create an English speaking environment by encouraging the students to use English in the classroom to make it a habit, letting them watch films or videos in English and the teachers should also use English in the classroom frequently so that the students have more exposure to the language. Teachers of English language are recommended to encourage their students to learn literature in order to develop their performance especially in speaking skills.

4. Teachers of English language should consider their students' linguistic abilities and minimize the amount of difficult vocabulary that their students encounter when studying literature. They have to use suitable teaching methods, approaches, strategies and materials that help the students in their acquisition of second language. Teachers are required to modify the difficult literary texts to suit the student's vocabulary without losing the essence of the original text. When studying literature, teachers should maintain

a comfortable and friendly atmosphere and design interesting activities that encourage students of literature to read, think and act.

5. . It is recommended that the community must have partnerships with wide range of community organizations like business and government agencies to provide critically needed materials, especially technologies. Also, teachers should establish and foster a community-based early language program through advocacy, Reese (2008). This type of community engagement emphasizes collaboration among school partners and sites, practical training for participants and reciprocal benefits through culturally rich language teaching as students and instructors learn to work with youngsters who are very open to novel ways of expressing ideas in a new language. A model is developed and presented as a concrete example of a successful award-winning program that language teachers might follow.

Steps for establishing Partnerships with Community Sites via Advocacy

Step 1:

- Finding a personnel
- Developing a vision

Step 2:

- Establishing contact with community centers

Step 3:

- Recruiting undergraduate college students

Step 4:

- Orientation and initial pedagogical training

Step 5:

- Co-teaching debriefing and ongoing training
6. Teachers are also encouraged to tackle this problem is to find the root of the problem and start from there. If the problem is cultural, that is in your culture it is unusual for students to talk out loud in class, or if students feel really shy about talking in front of other students then one way to go about breaking this barrier is to create and establish your own classroom culture where speaking is the norm. One way to do this is to distinguish your classroom from other classroom desks differently, in groups instead of lines etc.
 7. Language teachers are encouraged to set attainable goals from the start of the year. That is a surefire way for students to see how much they have grown. It is also necessary to give the students opportunity to choose what they learn— this will help them build their self-worth. Try a learning menu or choice board where students get to choose which activities they want to learn.

Hopefully, the study can contribute to the improvement of oral English accuracy teaching and learning at Aeta Magbuken students in Limay National High School.